

Digital

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Digital, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator “Individuals with basic or above basic overall digital skills in 2021” and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Individuals with basic or above basic overall digital skills in 2021 (in percent)

The indicator gives the percentage of individuals whose information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving skills are at basic or above basic level.

Source

Eurostat, <https://tinyurl.com/source-snd> (accessed 25 January 2023)

Note

Data for Kosovo* not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Supporting the digital transformation of the Western Balkan

Regional Indicators

Digital Education Stakeholder Forum 2022 – with WB participation

Legend: On track or maintaining achievement | Moderately improving, Challenges remain | Stagnating, Significant challenges | Decreasing, Major challenges | Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: good medium to be improved information not provided

Rapid transformative technological development for a competitive Western Balkans region A Europe fit for the digital age

	Development and linking of Digital Innovation Hubs	Digital education Communities of Practice/Digital Edu Hub	Digital skills development and virtual learning	MNE, MK & RS joining EuroHPC JU	Participation in Digital Europe Programme
Albania	Digital hub created Partnerships not yet established	No WB partners involved No activities implemented	No publicly funded initiative at central level		Association agreement signed
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Several digital hubs created with established partnerships	Few WB partners involved Large number of activities implemented	Publicly funded initiatives in place, number of participants not provided		No, lobbying process at national level started
Kosovo*	Digital hub created Info on partnerships not provided	Few WB partners involved Info on activities implemented not provided	Publicly funded initiative in place with considerable number of participants		Negotiations concluded
Montenegro	Digital hubs created Info on partnerships not provided	No WB partners involved No activities implemented	Information on publicly funded initiative and participants not provided	Joined	Association agreement signed
North Macedonia	Digital hub created with established partnerships	Information on WB partners involved and activities implemented not provided	Information on publicly funded initiative and participants not provided	Joined	Association agreement signed
Serbia	Several digital hubs created with established partnerships	Few WB partners involved Info on activities implemented not provided	Publicly funded initiatives in place with considerable number of participants	Joined	Association agreement signed

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